

THE ARCHITECTURE OF IDEAL LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS

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Abstract

Educational spaces and their design is one of the most influential factors in learning, among which the classroom is considered as the main learning environment in the educational space and is responsible for responding to people and their changing needs. Therefore, the educational space should have the necessary coordination with the age and educational level of students, considering that educational spaces have the greatest effect and role on the mentality and civilization of society. In some industrialized countries, due to the importance, they attach to educating the next generation, using appropriate models and standards, they design spaces that, while having engineering and architectural techniques, have also been considered from the angles of educational sciences and psychology. In this research, to achieve an ideal and flexible classroom, descriptive and analytical methods, library documentation techniques have been used and we will have an overview of environmental factors using architectural topics to facilitate the learning of students to better convey curriculum. By professors. Because these cases have a significant impact on the learning process of students and also on the quality, health, and desirability of the learning environment.

Key word: Phycology environment, interior design, education spaces

Introduction

In modern life, it is a well-known fact that humans spend most of their time in man-made environments. Humans live at home, study in schools, work in offices, travel with vehicles and are in constant contact with the physical environment (Nourmusavi 2020). Research has shown that many behavioral disorders in urban communities, such as violence, aggression, violation of the rights of others, and disobedience to the law, have historical, cultural, and economic roots in the quality of residential, educational, and workspaces; This is a proof of the importance of spatial quality. The physical environment with its constituent elements such as color, texture, light shadow, light, sound, form, etc. affects the human body and mind (Anbari 2015). Therefore, proper design of these spaces and observance of standards and quality indicators are important and effective factors in raising the quality level of educational spaces (Zaeghami 2013). An effective learning environment is an environment that, along with other influential components in the education of children, such as the curriculum, teachers, etc., has an important impact on the education of children. However, the physical environment of the school is only one of the influential components in learning; But it can be said that the most important component in an active learning environment (De Gregori 2007). The need to reform the body of education is to create spaces related to student activities; Spaces that have appropriate conditions for the physical, mental, emotional, and social development of children, which can be achieved by designing the details of the spaces according to the behavioral patterns of students (Torkaman 2016). Functional indicators and aesthetic principles and foundations in the design of physical educational spaces, in addition to meeting the mental and physical needs of students, will also nurture their talents and flourish their creativity (Tohidi 2018).

Problem-solving and the need to study it

Space with all its features plays an effective role in shaping people's personalities. This space is especially important for the growth of students, a factor that should have a positive effect on their physical and mental development (Serafat 2017). Today, most of the buildings that are used as scientific or cultural centers for students fit their real needs, neither in terms of their architecture nor in terms of the type of activities (Nasr 2017). Students need spaces for play and learning that, while controllable, do not limit them, are attractive, and are more of a movement than a pause. Students are more interested in experimentation than anything else. Spaces designed for students, especially educational spaces, should be able to influence their mental and emotional forces and thus participate in their education and create a happy and energetic environment for them (Azmodeh 2012,5).

One of the most important goals of this research is to:

1. Describe a suitable training place with the necessary standards
2. Describe the principles and criteria of design

Methodology

The main areas in this research include the design of educational spaces, child developmental psychology, and educational psychology of children. The purpose of this article is to explain how to design educational spaces following the spirits of children and at the same time efficient in education. Examining the subject of different capabilities of spaces appropriate to the behavioral patterns and needs of children in schools, including The ability of spaces appropriate to children's moods for their physical, mental, social, and emotional development, the ability of these spaces to affect the mental and emotional forces of the child, the ability of these spaces to participate in educating the child while creating a happy and energetic environment, The ability of these spaces in creating a desire in children to participate in the educational environment that forms the body of this article. At this stage of the research, referring to the researches done in the fields close to the research subject and qualitative method and logical reasoning have been used to analyze and present the results.

Literature Review

In this part of the research, a summary of the results of studies conducted on the articles of researchers and scholars in the fields close to the subject of the article was summarized in the following table, which shows the factors affecting children's learning.

Key results	Article / Project / Report Title	researcher
<ol style="list-style-type: none">i. Determining the effective criteria in choosing the type of school space organizationii. Appropriate model for designing educational spaceiii. Possibility of creating a space for comprehensive communication	Strategies for optimizing educational spaces	Halim bordi hagh nia, Rahim bordi hagh nia (2016)
<ol style="list-style-type: none">iv. colorv. lightvi. ceilingvii. soundviii. furniture	Application of environmental psychology in the design of educational spaces	Farzaneh kian abri, marzie tabaeian (2016)
<ol style="list-style-type: none">ix. Observance of standardx. Partitioningxi. arrangement of school furniture	How to design educational spaces from a psychological point of	Mahbobe tohidi, ahmad mirza kochak khoshnevis (2018),

xii.	doors and windows	view with the aim of achieving a standard classroom	
xiii. xiv.	Technology Classes Teaching Strategies	Environment-Behaviour Studies in the Classroom	Sandra Horne Martin, (2009)
xv. xvi. xvii.	play, Playgrounds and Nature Aesthetics and Unusual Spaces Flexible Spaces and Furnishings	ENVIRONMENTAL PSYCHOLOGY IN CLASSROOM DESIGN	KATIE HUNTER (2005)
xviii. xix. xx. xxi.	Sex of the subjects Age of the subjects Creating spaces based on children's age and releasing energy Using architectural forms appropriate to children	Child-oriented architecture from the perspective of environmental psychology	Maral Anbari, Hossein Soltanzadeh, (2015)
xxii. xxiii. xxiv.	Educational space Smart physical environment Air quality	Factors of interior design of education spaces by emphasis on Environment psychology principles	Sara Davarpanah (2017)
i. ii. iii.	Prioritize furniture Recognize the factors affecting success Diagnose student academic failure	The effect of satisfaction with the quality of educational space architecture on academic success	Vahid vaziri (2017)
iv. v. vi.	learning level quality of learning learning environments	The role of architecture and physical factors of educational environment on facilitating learning	Mozhgan torkaman (2016)
vii. viii.	School design Teaching place analysis	Designing Sustainable Schools as Three Dimensional Textbooks	Ester Ehrlich Schwartz (2013)
ix. x. xi.	Comfortable chairs and work spaces Classroom layout is changeable FromUse attractive colors, textures and patterns to cover floors and walls	School facilities	Henri (2001)
xii.	Outdoor spaces include green spaces and play areas	The effect of school architecture on academic achievement	Taner (2000)
xiii. xiv.	Not old school building Proper heating in the classrooms	Physical facilities and students' academic achievement	Earthman (2002)

The educational method with emphasis on the development of outdoor education causes diversity in the curriculum so that different ideas are presented on how to use nature for education in different conditions and according to different cultures and conditions and the situation of each lesson and teacher. What all these ideas have in common is that it motivates the teacher and the student to pursue learning outcomes beyond the classroom. This shows that this method of education does not believe that extracurricular education is better than classroom-

based education; Rather, it only indicates that some lessons are better presented outside the classroom environment, and in a more general sense, in-class lessons should be combined with out-of-class lessons (Higgins, Peter, and Nicol, Robbie 2002).

The effect of environmental factors on learning and behavior in educational environments

Environmental psychology is a subset of the behavioral sciences. This debate dates back to the early 1960s. Looking at the history of this field, we find that in the 1960s and 1970s, the field of environmental psychology and research in general that examined the impact of the environment on various human behaviors, Has been a significant issue (Kamelnia 2010) The first work of environmental psychology was to consider the effects of physical and social environment on individuals. But since the 1980s, the role of people in the environment has also been studied. This field of psychology is an interdisciplinary branch that is closely related to architecture, landscape architecture, and urban design (Tabaian 2016). The field of environmental psychology emphasizes how the physical environment affects emotions and behaviors (Ata 2012).

Numerous studies show that the quality of the environment in which a person works, ie factors such as space, color, light, sound, and the amount of enjoyment of space, affect his perception. For this reason, the relationship between architecture and psychology is necessary for the better design of spaces (Tabaian 2016). The beautiful school facilitates learning, brings vitality and vitality to children and adolescents, and inappropriate school, narrow and dark, soulless, boredom and depression for students, and the rate of active learning and presence and lively They harm school (Roghani 2016). To achieve the desired educational environment, one must first identify the needs of age groups. Meanwhile, the study of behavioral patterns in educational settings will facilitate the recognition of needs. Barker, an ecological psychologist, agrees There is a special relationship between the physical dimensions of architecture and behavior (physical behavioral sites). In this regard, classroom benches, how they are arranged will affect their behavior and learning. (Ghafari 2000)

Features of a safe and ideal school

School is a familiar environment in which the user feels relaxed and knows where everything is and can focus while no one disturbs him. Having a safe space is also necessary for a group of several people. Without such an atmosphere, social communication with others would be impossible. Because if you do not have the space to say it belongs to you, you can not understand your situation. This is why it is so important for children to be able to place objects they have made in the classroom, such as handicrafts, in places that they are sure of and do not fear will be damaged (Hertzberger 2008). To achieve the goals of ideal learning, it is necessary to have functional and appropriate spaces. One of the problems with designing a classroom is to provide a feature in the classroom that, while being dedicated to children's general activities and general education, can become spaces for their activities. During class time, there should be conditions for the teacher to control and monitor student activities. Classrooms should be flexible, for example, using removable partitions to achieve the desired spaces (Kamelnia 2007). According to the forecasts, 1.5 square meters of land and 5.5 cubic meters of air are required for each student. In other words, for a class of 30 people, the dimensions of the room should be 8 meters long, 6 to 7 meters wide, and 4 meters high. The required space for each student should not be 4.5 cubic meters and the height should be 3 meters less, so to choose a place for the class, the size of the class and the number of students should be considered (Haghnia 2016).

Five Recommended Factors for Classroom Design

1. An efficient classroom is the center for a variety of activities. Furniture and materials are directly determined by the type of activity. Shelves and furniture are used to define different sections, because children focus more on their activities if they are not distracted by other visible activities in the classroom.
2. Use sections related to study topics, divide and put each device in its place.

3. Furniture can be changed according to the type of activity.
4. Involve children in furniture and classroom makeup.
5. Putting a section to show daily activities and activity charts, etc. to increase the feeling of security and control (Kamelnia, 2007)

The role of architecture following the spirits of children for their physical, mental, social, and emotional development

1. **Stairs:** Perhaps for a long time there was the image that in indoor learning environments (especially for children) one should avoid creating level differences, but today in the interior design of schools, going up and down is an effective indicator of the quality of learning. Is. Therefore, the use of stairs and surface differences can be considered in this regard (Hertzberger 2008)
2. **Variety of ceilings:** in the interior design of learning environments Paying attention to the ceiling as one of the components that form the space can be effective in defining the different qualities of indoor spaces. The use of sloping roofs, in addition to creating diversity in the space, contains themes of spatial semiotics for children (cottage memory). (Turkman 2016)
3. **Corridors:** In architecture for children, the design of connecting spaces and pause spaces is as important as space itself. Communication spaces for adults are only a place to communicate between rooms, but for children, they are a place to perform various experiences freely and free from the shackles inside the room. In addition, by creating pause spaces in the corridors, the corridors look less narrow, dark, and long, and it is more attractive to continue the way. On the other hand, by creating one-way corridors that allow communication with the outside space, the child will no longer feel trapped in space; But because one-way corridors are not economically and energy-efficient, this problem can be mitigated by a combination of one-way and two-way corridors (Azmoddeh, 2012)

The role of architecture appropriate to children's moods in influencing the child's mental and emotional forces

1. **Light:** The psychological effects of light in children's educational spaces Light are the first condition for any kind of visual perception. In absolute darkness, we can see neither space nor form and color. But light is not only a physical necessity, but its psychological value is one of the most important factors in human life in all fields (Groter 2007). Natural light means the same as daylight from the sun. Environmentalists place great emphasis on the use of daylight in educational spaces. Research shows that the use of natural light not only plays a major role in learning but can also affect students' health and attention (Hawes 2012).

Due to the importance of lighting for the environment, there are points that are as follows

1. The reflection of light in water and light elements in water create pleasant sensory perceptions.
2. The use of stained glass and skylights is recommended to diversify the spaces.
3. The light source should not be in the view of students because it causes glare
4. It is better to have the classrooms to the north and south, and also to the east and west of the building to prevent direct sunlight from entering the space.
5. Tall and large windows let more light into the classroom and turn it on. More air enters the classroom and provides students with the need for more air. Large and large windows bring a feeling of freedom and unrestrainedness. (Mahmoodi 2011)
6. The intensity of light received depends on the design and size of the window, for classrooms in general, windows with an area of 30 to 60 percent of the facade area or about 15 to 30 percent of the classroom area are suitable.
7. Class window levels should not be less than 4 5 to 4 9 class levels.
8. The minimum amount of lighting required in the class is 200 lux and the maximum is 500 lux (Shojaei 2009)

The predominance of color and form

Most children under school age, the ages between 3 to 6 years show strong interest in colors, but at the age of 7 to 9 years pay attention to forms, and this interest is maximized at age 9 years old. As the child grows up, the tendency to nature and form is increased. But in a survey, about 10 percent of pre-elementary children have shown that they tend to dominate the form to the colors. Children who overcome a form more than the colors in terms of IQ are more clever than alleged color groups. But some theorists believe that ingenuity and creativity are more in alleged color groups. Studies on documents related to children about the colors showed, the color orange, and then red and pink are favorite colors for children between the ages of 3 to 6 years old. According to Ashley, applying colors with awareness and knowledge of its relationship with the child's life excitement is concluded that red color is a superior color for children and overalls for children act based on their emotions. As they become older and can control their feelings, they get interested in cold colors. Researches showed that red color has two contrasting features:

first the feeling of affection and love, and the second induces a sense of attack and harness because red colors are closely associated with very intense feelings. Blue is associated with emotional control. Researchers have found that children are also interested in brown. However, scientists have discovered the fact that children who have a tendency towards blue, may have very severe emotions in some cases that modify it or change its direction.

Table 1: Psychology of colors and how to use them in spaces (Anbari 2015)

How to use it in spaces	Specifications	Color	No
Using it in the environments of game, show and sport	warm color and stimulating Passion and love, sincerity	Red	1
For Educational spaces in elementary school – due to the prevention of drowsiness and lethargy in children ... lively, invigorating, warm peace of the children	Energizing and stimulating color	Orange	2
Its combination with other colors and use it in the space of rest	indicating Love and romance	Pink	3
It is better to use the color with combination with other colors in classes and educational spaces	Expresses the sense of relief – represents peace, security and order-expresses the feeling of sorrow, introspection and isolation in some people	Blue	4
To make interior decoration happy and bright	Warm and happy color- stimulating thought- making eyes bored more than other colors	Yellow	5
For decorating studying rooms, educational spaces and a place needs concentration.	Cool color and a symbol of nature represents peace, happiness, health and jealousy, gaining the ability to read	Green	6
Pale violet spectrum in space and educational environment, gives peace and happiness. as a result it can be used practical and craft classes .	The most spiritual color represents harmony between reason and emotion and border between spirituality and materialism	Purple	7

Table 2: Psychology of forms and how to use them in spaces (Anbari 2015)

The place of use	Excited emotions	Form	No
Child's play space	Imaginery-creative imagination	Irregular forms	1
Entrance	Caller	Concave form	2
emphasis points and pausing space	Innovation and complexity	Static form	3
	Suggests the status of rejecting	Convex form	4
Children love the spaces	Softness and comfort	Soft and arched form	5
Passage	Comfort and mobility	horizontally Expanded form	6
	Hard	Angular and broken forms	7

researchers have found that there is a close relationship between selecting colors and genders; so that in the ages between 6 to 17 years old girls consider warm colors and boys consider cool colors but as they grow up this status gets reversed. In terms of physical physiology, certain colors are considered to be associated with various diseases, and as a sample table, 1 can be considered and apply proper colors for any spaces regarding its psychological features, and table 2 can be considered to apply suitable forms for children in designing spaces for them. (Anbari 2015).

The role of architecture in participating in the education of children at the same time creating a happy and full of energy environment

1. **Noise:** Continuous and unpredictable noise causes body fatigue and reduced field of vision, color recognition, and ultimately reduced student work efficiency. The results of the research of the scientists of the University of Alburg on the echo of sound in the classroom show that in classrooms where there are no carpets and curtains and their chairs are made of wood or metal and the fabric is not used, the sound stays in the space longer. Thus, the classroom is full of unnecessary sounds such as whispers and rustling of paper, etc. And sometimes the teacher speaks loudly to overshadow the sounds, which is undesirable for students (Shahbazi 2015). Also, unfortunately, due to the wrong location of many schools in our country, educational environments can cause noise pollution, and vice versa, in some schools, noise pollution prevents communication between students and teachers. In this case, slow children and those with hearing problems are most affected. The school should be designed for everyone. (Tawhidi 2016)
2. **Heat and cold:** (Turkman 2016) examines the effect of class temperature and wind and rainy weather on students' behavior and shows the effect of such physical factors of the environment on behavior. In research that was conducted for two consecutive years in the first and second grades of elementary school using field observation, 48 teachers completed questionnaires. From the above questionnaires, two factors were named: the amount of effort (the amount of effort and cooperation with the teacher) and the number of class activities and mobility. Then the relationship between these two behavioral aspects with air temperature and other air characteristics (humidity, wind, and rain) in the morning and afternoon was re-examined. This study shows that students' behavior is significantly affected by temperature and air quality. For

example, a temperature of more than 2 degrees Celsius reduces students' mobility and lethargy (Moinpour, 2004)

- 3. Organizing and arranging the class:** The most important change in educational spaces is breaking the line of view of teachers and students and creating space for students to interact with each other. For this purpose, linear rows are contrary to the students' mood. In traditional classrooms, where students' chairs are arranged in regular rows and the teacher's desk is placed in front of the classroom, all attention is focused on the teacher and there is little communication between students (Jalalian 2016).

This order may be very desirable when the teacher provides a lesson for the whole class, but it makes learning from classmates and group work impossible. The students in the last row of the class are far away from the teacher and are likely to be easy to cause disciplinary problems and disorders. (Dejdar 2016) In some classes, chairs are arranged around the desks and the teacher's desk is placed on the sidewalk. This type of arrangement is organized in experimental science classes. Students work with each other. If the facilities of the classroom are such that the students are arranged in a circle or can interact with the teacher, then the teacher is a part of the students and can, in addition to teaching, also guide and lead the students' group discussions. However, when considering how classrooms are arranged, it is important to consider all students. One of the basic needs of children is to be noticed by teachers and if the physical space of the classroom encourages this feeling in students, without a doubt, the number of disciplinary issues and problems will be significantly reduced (Siami 2001).

Interior design patterns in learning environments

All components of interior architecture should be in line with the development of different learning skills of children and have an effective role in this regard. For example, the use of the flooring that can teach children topics (such as multiplication tables, alphabet, etc.) or even a tool for children to play and have fun, can be attractive. (Jalalian 2016). There are different design patterns for a learning environment. These patterns can be considered in different areas; From how the school is organized and related to the context to the design of the smallest interior components (such as door handles) are all among the items that can be very important. (Turkman 2016)

- 1. Learning Streets:** School corridors became learning streets with a variety of activities; These include conversation and discussion spaces, seating areas, small workstations, individual wardrobes for children, work shows, and workshops. Corridors are the expandable spaces of classrooms and their extensions (Dezhdar 2016)

The role of architecture in creating a desire in children to participate in the educational environment

- 1. Inviting entries:** For the child, the most important motivating factor for going to school is seeing his friends; Therefore, if the entrance to space is designed in such a way that before the child enters the space, a picture of the presence of other children is shown to him, the best kind of invitation will happen. The installation of a separate entrance and indicator for children also increases their desire to enter. (Jalalian 2016)
- 2. Water and trees:** The presence of elements that are mostly seen in the natural environment, such as water and trees, can add a sense of vitality to the educational space; Therefore, not only in terms of the quality of the space created but also as an effective factor on the children's sense of belonging to the environment and nature and the teaching of natural life and related skills can be considered (Jalalian 2016)

Internal and external communication (role of nature in education)

Louis Kahn defines the word school in this way: all the places that man uses to satisfy his desire for learning are called schools, and these places are not only for learning and learning ideas and theories; They are also used to understand the reasons for the existence of everything and the mutual occasions and relations between man and nature. The presence of nature in educational spaces often occurs in

a very limited way, and this limited presence takes place without taking into account the special needs of children and the high capabilities of natural environments in meeting these needs. It is necessary to design natural environments in schools to meet the different needs of children in development, education, and skills training. The importance of the presence of nature and outdoor spaces in schools has been considered by child researchers from various aspects. The study of educational theories shows that children's educators pay attention to extracurricular education along with in-class education and the use of nature as an educational tool has received much attention today. It is also a very suitable platform for nurturing different aspects of a child's development. Also, the existence of natural spaces creates peace of mind, the freshness of space, and a sense of belonging to more children than the school space. How to design outdoor spaces and the quality of nature's presence in it varies according to each of the mentioned aspects for children and should be considered by designers. How (presence of nature and correct design methods for this can affect the quality of education of children (Muzaffar 2009)

Conclusion

According to the issues raised in the psychology of child development and education and research, as stated, different factors affect the child's learning, one of which is the learning environment. A school with a sufficient and standard space suitable for children can affect children, the development of talents, the formation of personality and moral and social values, and finally on the rate of their learning, and create a good foundation for his future education. Be fruitful for the next generation, Its buildings must be creative, not imitated. Be a stimulating environment for free thought and creative expression. In this case, in this type of school, the child shows a great desire to attend it and it affects the child in such a way that it can even make him dependent on himself. Finally, the basis of each student's interest in learning is formed by attending school and being in an educational environment. It will make the child disgusted and disgusted with similar environments and even have lasting negative effects on his personality. The results of the studies are summarized that the summary of this research can be seen in Figures 1.

This model consists of two parts

1. factors affecting children's learning
2. factors that affect learning.

Figure 1 Analytical model of effective and influential factors of appropriate learning

According to the studies, as shown in Figure 1, different factors affect the level of learning, one of which is the learning environment. The educational space includes architecture and physical factors. In this study, these cases and their effect on students' level of learning have been studied. Factors affecting learning are also related to the amount of education and learning that the child benefits from in exchange with his educational environment and the variables of the educational environment represent the characteristics and features of the educational environment. Factors that affect children's learning are: 1 Dimension of space 2 Colors 3 Light 4 Sound 5 How much one enjoys that space 6 Variety 7 Sound comfort 8 Thermal comfort 9 Equipment 10 Nature and the existence of open spaces as these factors The creator of the environment is mentioned. The quality of the environment in which a person is educated, ie factors such as space, color, light, and sound and the amount of enjoyment of that space based on studies have been proposed that these factors can affect the quality of students learning in different ways. For example, one of the constructive factors of the educational environment that can affect the level of learning of the child is the factor of diversity, which is considered in the presence of diversity both in the furniture of the educational sector and in the existence of various spaces such as learning gardens and educational corridors. In the process of space design, considering the mental and physical characteristics of children and various principles that exist in the field of design, such as creating social communication, paying attention to aesthetics and observing special safety rules for children, paying attention to the shape and arrangement of classes, color, light, and ventilation. Educational facilities, interior decoration, etc. Educational environments can be created that address child, It challenges and draws their attention by creating desire so that they can observe and think without thinking and be educated in this way, and based on this, it has improved their level of learning through architecture. Paying attention to the mental and physical characteristics of children in designing educational spaces can help children to learn and develop their talents and ultimately to their growth and flourishing. Paying attention to children's moods and characteristics and designing educational spaces based on their characteristics Attendance in the educational environment and as a result increase and facilitate their learning. In such a way that when children are in an environment where they observe that everything is made according to their spirits and their mental and physical characteristics are noticed and respected, their enthusiasm for being in this space and learning new things is doubled and even causes a lot of growth and prosperity. It becomes their talents. Educational spaces are prone to dryness due to their special limitations, but every effort should be made to prevent this from happening. Giving importance to educational spaces and observing the principles and standards related to them in the design of these centers leads to the creation of an environment appropriate to the psychological needs of students and, consequently, society. In general, some of the important results obtained indicate this The expansion of education from the closed space of the classroom to the open space and in fact, the tangibility of scientific content for children through play or communication with nature has a significant effect on creating a child's interest in the learning environment, which will play a significant role in facilitating child learning. The existence of various spaces in terms of variety in form and quality of light and use, as well as the existence of differences in different levels in the educational environment, cause a sense of curiosity and physical activity in children, which results in depression and boredom through proper discharge of energy. And environments are provided in which the child himself, with motivation and curiosity, seeks to discover problems, and finally, with the achievement of the result and the answer to his question, learning takes place in his mind. Because one of the most important needs in childhood is to establish a friendly and social relationship in the peer group. Creating spaces in which these interactions take place easily teaches this skill to children, and also in these spaces, many important topics are exchanged through these friendly connections between children, which makes this part of learning possible. When a child feels that he is in an environment in which attention is paid to his mental and physiological characteristics, and in fact, that environment is designed for him, he finds more desire to be present and stay in that environment, which ultimately facilitates learning. In general, designing spaces following children's behavioral patterns and their mental characteristics in schools should be able to meet three

specific categories of children's needs. These needs include educational needs, nurturing needs (social growth and physical growth), and spiritual and emotional needs. Meeting these needs makes the physical environment of schools an effective environment for the educational purposes of children. Designed spaces should be a good platform for children's physical and social development. Social spaces that are designed in educational environments allow children to interact, communicate and confront each other, and group and individual play spaces promote the physical and social development of children. Finally, from the study of studies conducted, it is concluded that the environmental factors studied in the field of education affect student learning; This influence is such that the combination of these factors together provide the conditions for the student to focus more easily on the subject matter. On the other hand, it creates better conditions for the teacher so that he can also convey the lesson materials to the students better; In this way, it facilitates learning students.

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